

**IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON
EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN AN
ORGANISATION**

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CONCEPT OF MOTIVATION IN EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN AN ORGANISATION

WHAT IS MOTIVATION

To Re'em (2011) motivation is coined from the Latin word *motus*, a form of the verb *movere*, which means to move, influence, affect, and excite. Motivation can also be defined as the act of providing motive that causes someone to act (Shanks, 2012).

Motivation is a key to any successful people management role. If you can encourage, persuade or develop your people in such ways as to improve their effectiveness, then the role of manager is seen as successful. Increasingly, as managers have to be super professionals in addition to their managerial responsibilities, it is even more important that motivation is achieved.

Motivation can be specified as a management process, which encourage people to work better for the overall benefit of the organization, by providing them motives, which are based on their unfulfilled needs.

The matters arising is: “why managers need to motivate employees?” (Herzberg, 1959). According to Smith (1994) it is because of the survival of the company. Amabile (1993) contributed to this statement by arguing that it is necessary for managers and leaders of organization to learn to understand and effectively deal with their employee's motivation; since motivated employees' are the pillars of successful organization in present and future century. She also indicates that unmotivated employees may probably contribute little effort in their jobs, stay away from workplace as much as possible, go out of the organization and make low quality of work. When employees are well motivated, they help the organization to grow and survive in a fast changing workplaces (Lindner 1998, 36). Lindner also indicates that the most difficult role of managers is to motivate employee, because what motivates employees changes always (Bowen and Radhakrishna 1991, 16-22).

The term motivation was developed in the early 1880's, prior to that time, the term “will” was used by well-known philosophers as well as notable social theorists when talking motivated human behaviours (Forgas, Williams and Laham 2005, 86). According to them motivation is believed to be; *an entity that compelled one to action*. Recently, many researchers has offered unique definitions of motivation.

It has been defined as; *the psychological process that gives behaviour purpose and direction* (Kreitner 1995, 168); *a predisposition to behave in a purposive manner to achieve specific, unmet needs* (Buford, Bedeian & Lindner 1995, 31-34); *an internal drive to satisfy an unsatisfied need* (Higgins 1994, 114).

It is apparent that managers needs to motivate employees if they want to get the necessary results for the organization. It can also be said that there is an agreement about the facts that motivation is an

in-dividual development, it is depicted as being deliberate, it has several sides and the aim of motivational theories is to predict behaviours. It appears that Herzberg and Maslow theories are still been used to-day because they were among the first researchers at this topic.

Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation originates from within the individual and causes the individual to feel stimulated internally (Re'em, 2011). According to Burton (2012) intrinsic motivation is more about an individual's self-satisfaction and the reward is normally within the action itself and does not need external factors to influence behavior.

Extrinsic Motivation

People sometimes people act because external factors have influenced them or prompted them to act in a certain way, and this is referred to as extrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). As opposed to intrinsic motivation where the reward of the action is within the action itself, for extrinsic motivation the outcome or reward is separable from the activity itself (Re'em, 2011).

The relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation

The difference between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is apparent, yet researchers argues that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation also have an effect on each other. Deci (1972) claims that in some cases extrinsic motivation can minify intrinsic motivation. He argues that if money is administered contingently, it minifies intrinsic motivation. But this event will not occur if the money is non-contingently distributed. Amabile (1993) respond to this discussion by stating that although extrinsic motivation can work in opposition to intrinsic motivation, it can also have a reinforcing effect: "once the scaffolding of extrinsic motivation is taken care of, intrinsic motivation can lead to high levels of satisfaction and performance". She went further to state in her research that both intrinsic and extrinsic values can motivate employees to do their respective work, however intrinsic and extrinsic motivation can have very different effects on employees. (Amabile 1993, 185-201)

In conclusion, it can be stated that employees can be intrinsically and or extrinsically motivated to carry out certain work (Amabile, 1993), and that extrinsic and intrinsic motivation can reinforce each other, but in some cases extrinsic motivators can also minify intrinsic motivation (Deci 1972, 14-23). Moreover, researchers, argue that not all people are evenly motivated, some employees are more intrinsically and others are more extrinsically motivated (Furnham et al 1998, 1035-1043).

Motivation in the workplace is a broadly researched topic (Rynes et al 2004, 381-394) earlier research has been conducted by Maslow (1943) and Herzberg (1959), who were innovators at their subject.

Many definition has been composed, e.g. Herzberg's definition of motivation in the workplace is: performing a work related action because you want to (Herzberg, 1959). Some divergence took place about the important of certain aspects, but consensus is in the fact that motivation is an individual process, it is described as being deliberate, it is multifaceted and that the purpose of motivational theories is to predict behavior (Mitchell 1982, 80-88.)

The difference between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is also explained. Namely, individuals are intrinsically motivated when they look for pleasure, interest, satisfaction, enjoyment and curiosity, self-expression or personal challenges in the work. And individual are extrinsically motivated when they engage in the work in order to gain some goal that is apart from the work itself (Amabile, 1993). Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators are necessary in motivating employees (Herzberg, 1959). It must be argued that managers must not only concentrate on the necessary factors, since, according to Herzberg (1959) managers need to address all hygiene and motivator factors to motivate employees (Saiyadain 2009, 158).

EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION

Many factors like environment, capital and human resources influences how organization performs. Though human resources is seen as having the most influence on the performance of organization. It is legitimate thus to debate that an organization needs to motivate its employees in order to accomplish its stated goals and objectives. In this chapter motivation is well explained. It is obvious that motivation has been perceived in numerous ways. Many researchers have tried to come up with a concise theory to formulate motivation but all bring in different ideas. Research has been conducted about this subject and many theories were designed which greatly influence organizational behavior. For example Herzberg's theory of motivation (1959) is still used nowadays. According to Staw (1976) Herzberg was one of the first persons who distinguished between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. That distinction has clarified and also helped in motivating employees at workplace (Staw 1976, 49-52).

■ BENEFITS TO THE MANAGER

Motivation is essentially about **commitment to doing something**. In the context of a business, motivation can be said to be about

"The will to work"

However, motivation is about more than simply working hard or completing tasks. Entrepreneurs and staff can find motivation from a variety of sources.

Motivation can come from the enjoyment of the work itself and/or from the desire to achieve certain goals e.g. earn more money or achieve promotion.

It can also come from the sense of satisfaction gained from completing something, or achieving a successful outcome after a difficult project or problem solved.

Why does motivation matter in business? In short, people's behaviour is determined by what motivates them. The performance of employees is a product of both their abilities (e.g. skills & experience) and motivation. A talented employee who feels de-motivated is unlikely to perform well at work, whereas a motivated employee can often deliver far more than is expected from them!

Benefits of a well-motivated workforce

A well-motivated workforce can provide several advantages:

Better productivity (amount produced per employee). This can lead to lower unit costs of production and so enable a firm to sell its product at a lower price

Lower levels of absenteeism as the employees are content with their working lives

Lower levels of staff turnover (the number of employees leaving the business). This can lead to lower training and recruitment costs

Improved industrial relations with trade unions

Contented workers give the firm a **good reputation** as an employer so making it easier to recruit the best workers

Motivated employees are likely to **improve product quality** or the customer service associated with a product.

THEORIES OF MOTIVATION

Exploring Motivation Theories

In the HRM process motivation seems to be one of the most important function yet it's the least understood aspect. Many researchers have conducted many studies about motivation and what they have discovered is that human behaviour is quite complex thus it has been really difficult to figure out what motivates various employees. To be able to have a complete understanding of what motivation is one has to think of it as a multifaceted process that encompasses individual, managerial and organizational implications (Decenzo et al. 2007). This means that it does not only rely on the behaviour exhibited by an employee rather there are other factors that influence an individual to be motivated depending on the job they are doing.

In the corporate world today, organizations have realized that employee motivation is of key importance if any sustainable company growth and success is to be realized and maintained. Top managers are working day and night trying to find means to stay at the top of their game amid harsh economic times and tough competition. Those companies who have taken upon themselves to ensure that their employees are constantly motivated have been able to succeed in not only gaining high revenues but also have good relationships with their workers.

Through investing in the employees more companies are coming to the realization that the triggers that end up motivating people are different and also unique. A lot of people would say money is the best way to motivate people, however it is not the final answer, in-fact in some cases it encourages job hopping when the extra bonuses stop coming through. Moreover money seldom motivates because it is never enough and available, the extra cash left after company expenditures is not adequate to meet constant income increments (Gellerman 1968).

Others may claim that they are motivated because they want to make a difference in their workplace and even the world, whatever the reasons are for one to be motivated to reach peak performance it has to be managed and also balanced (Glenn 2012). Before getting into the various motivation theories that organizations could adopt to in order to achieve high levels of performance it is important to first of all understand and define what motivation is and its origin.

The term motivation originated from the Latin word *movere* which means “to move” (Szilagyi, Wallace 1990). It is also derived from the term motive which in simple terms is an emotion or desire to incite action. Motivation can therefore be defined as a state of being incited to action. Moreover it is clear that motivation is based on a consciousness thus it has to come from within an individual though sometimes it can be externally induced. Work motivation on the other hand dwells more on the domain of careers and work. In most cases work motivation has heavily relied on the motivation to perform or produce, however being that the work place can be diverse one could argue that there are different angles to look at it: For example motivation to keep a job or quit the company all-together, motivation to collaborate with others through sharing the skills and knowledge one has, motivation to be a leader or even the motivation to start a new venture (Clegg, Bailey 2008, 919).

According to Locke and Latham motivation refers to the intrinsic factors that stimulate action while the external factors play a role of prompting the action (Locke, Latham 2004). Hutchinson describes motivation as energy exerted by an individual towards a certain activity. It is something that is within an individual that forces or instigates a person to make a choice of action. Motivation can therefore not be confined as a behavior or performance it is a mixture of many factors (Hutchinson 2013). There are two broad categories of motivation, extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation emanates from tangible rewards that are external and partly beyond the control of the one receiving them e.g. pay, retirement benefits, healthcare plan. Intrinsic motivation refers to motivation that emerges from within a person e.g. feelings of self-esteem, accomplishment, recognition etc. (Hutchinson 2013). It is important to note that motivation is not the same as “job satisfaction“. The two however are intertwined but only to a certain degree, job satisfaction can be regarded as motivation but does not necessarily aim at motivating high productivity instead it corresponds mostly to negative turnover (Clegg et al. 2008, 920).

The next section will now discuss the various motivation theories primarily studied by different scholars and their contribution works to motivation theories. These theories can be adopted by organizations aiming to motivate their workforce so as to reach high performance levels and achieve the set goals significant for the company. The section will review content and process theories and in addition reinforcement theories of motivation

Content Theories

The content motivation theories refers to “what” energizes people to be motivated. This type of theories focuses more on the interests of a person’s goals, needs and motives and the incentives that causes them to be driven to behave in a particular manner. The various motivational theorists that have looked into this type of theory includes the works of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs, Herzberg’s motivator-hygiene theory, Alderfer’s ERG theory and McClelland need theory (Szilagyi, et al. 1990).

Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs

The Maslow’s hierarchy of needs is a theory that was developed between the years 1943 – 1954 by a man called Abraham Maslow. He further went and categorized this theory into five classification of needs as shown in Figure 2 below. The classification starts from the bottom going up in this order: physiological needs, safety needs, love/belonging, self-esteem and finally self-actualization.

Figure 2: Maslow’s Hierarchy of needs

Maslow’s theory claims that in a work place setting, the people are motivated to perform because of desire to satisfy a set of internal needs. His theory is based upon three principal assumptions. The first fundamental assumption is that, human beings have needs that can influence their behavior. The needs that are unsatisfied can definitely influence behavior where else the satisfied needs don’t act as motivators.

The second underlying assumption is that people arrange their needs according to how important they are. The hierarchy begins from basic needs such as food and shelter and ascends to complex levels such as Achievement and self-esteem. The final Primary assumption is that one can only advance to the next level of ranking only when the lower level of needs are at least minimally gratified. E.g. an employee may focus more on ensuring that he has satisfied the need of working in an area that is safe and free from any harm before he can direct his attention and motivation towards successfully achieving a given task (Szilagyi, et al. 1990).

According to Miner 1980 the needs of the theory are seen influencing a person's behavior unconsciously. Often the individual is usually oblivious of the motivational sources of his actions. Maslow presented a set category of human needs to explain the correlation between these set of needs and their influence to a person's behavior. The first set of the needs are called the physiological needs and are at the base of the pyramid as shown in fig. 2 above. In this group Maslow placed the chemical needs of the body such as: hunger, sleepiness, sexual desire, activity needs, desired sensory satisfactions, water etc. Most of these needs tend to have a narrowed corporal base e.g. hunger, thirst, sex but not for sleepiness. If these psychological needs are not met with full satisfaction, then the person's concentration is only centered with the object at hand, thus it is not a wonder a person who is very hungry or thirsty can only think of food and water (Miner, 1980).

Looking at physiological needs from an organizational dimension: providing workers with attractive wages or salaries is necessary for a good and fulfilled work life. One could also look at it from the working conditions point of view, having warm and well-lit working conditions helps the employees to conduct business operations with minimal disturbances thus progressive success for the company. Top managers could also introduce subsidized or even free catering services to ensure that the employees have ample time to meet up with their fellow colleagues as they enjoy brunch or lunch (Buchanan, Huczynski 1997).

The second level is the safety needs, this needs represents the need to be free of any kind of danger. Just like the physiological needs the safety needs have the same common quality. Naturally people are motivated to avoid danger at all costs, in this case danger could be represented in form of wild animals, extreme weather conditions, disease, and assault etc. definitely poses a threat to human safety. In the society we live in, especially among adults there is a tendency of inhibiting this type of motivation whereby the expression on the outer surface shows that no one is afraid of their safety thus making it difficult to see the existence of such needs on the surface.

It is for this reason that Maslow likened this sense of insecurity to that state of a young child whose strongest need is to protect himself against a threatening world (Miner 1980).

In a work setting perspective, these needs are combined to provide an environment that is safe and secure for the employee. This means that the employers have to provide the necessary tools required for the protection of their employees so that they don't end up harms-way as they conducting the given tasks. Having job security is of key importance to the employees. The organizations could also provide private health insurance covers for their employees and families to cater for them when they fall sick. Moreover providing attractive pension provisions assures the employees that their financial future is well secured even after they have retired (Buchanan et al. 1997).

The third level is the love/belonging needs, and in this ranking Maslow intentionally used the word love to represent affiliation and general belongingness. Having fully satisfied the physiological and safety needs, the social needs become dominant. They include, friendships, spouses, children, parents, group memberships and gratifying interactions with other people. In organizations, these needs could be expressed in the following ways: frequent interactions with fellow employees, supervision that is centered on the employees and acceptance by others. It is important for the employees to feel loved and accepted and that they have a sense of belonging at a workplace, therefore the top managers should encourage constant communication among themselves and their subordinates to ensure that employees have a voice in running the company operations. The organizations should also encourage the employees to work as a team rather than individuals so as to foster professional friendships and compatible working groups (Szilagyi, et al. 1990).

The fourth ranking in the Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory is the self- esteem needs which in other words could be referred to as the ego and status. These needs are segregated into two broad categories, with the first category being internally oriented needs that may emanate from desires of strength, adequacy, confidence, freedom and achievement. The second category represents esteem that could be

acquired through external sources, such prestige, notoriety, recognition, prominence and appreciation. Either way satisfying both categories leads to self-confidence whilst ignoring them may lead dire consequences like inferiority complex and sense of helplessness (Miner 1980).

This set of needs could be discussed in an organizational perspective, in that every individual in the company has the right to feel respected despite their position in the company. Employees also feel a sense of accomplishment when they perform a given task and succeed in it. By recognizing their efforts, it is a clear indication that organization notices what they are doing and could even go ahead and reward them with prestigious titles in the company or even job promotions. Regular positive feedback is also another channel that the top management could use to convey their message to the employees. By communicating and praising individuals for a job well done shows that they are pleased with the way the business operations are being carried out, thus boosting the confidence of the workers (Szilagyi, et al. 1990).

Self-actualization is the final ranking in the Maslow's hierarchy of needs and these needs are very significant and they include: morality, spontaneity, growth, advancement and achievement. For an individual to achieve these types of needs the other four needs have to be fully satisfied. Maslow described this as a sense of desire towards self-fulfilment for one to reach his potential and be self-actualized (Latham 2007). In an organization setting this need could be represented through allowing the employees to take on new challenging job assignments. By allowing them to do so, is an indication that the company gives freedom for their workers to develop and introduce new ideas thus a spontaneous and diverse workforce. The workers also get to have full foresight over the core work activities in the company (Buchanan et al. 1997).

The bottom-line to this theory is that as one level of needs gets fulfilled its vitality slowly recedes while the strength of the next need higher in the pecking order rises (Latham 2007). Since the theory relies more on human behaviour these needs could hold different value from one individual to the next: e.g. some upper level managers may place more emphasis on self-esteem and self-actualization needs in that they are more concerned with issues regarding career change and advancement while the lower level managers could be more interested on the safety and security needs (Szilagyi, et al. 1990). It is also important to note that this theory cannot be suitable for all types of work, however since the inception of this theory many organizations have integrated the Maslow's theory of needs in their company's policies to help change their practices for motivating employees (Buchanan et al. 1997).

Herzberg's Motivator- Hygiene Theory

Fredrick Herzberg is the man behind the motivation hygiene theory which he researched and published in his 1959 book "The Motivation to work". His theory is also referred to as the two- factor theory due to its two distinct groupings: the motivator factors that could lead to satisfaction at work if well fulfilled and the hygiene factors that contribute to dissatisfaction if they are thwarted. In his research fourteen factors are described as the sources of either good or bad feelings (Adair 2004).

According to Herzberg there are eight hygiene factors that could lead to job dissatisfaction if they are not well catered for from an organization point of view, they include: company policy and administration, whereby it is important for those policies relating to the employees to be readily available and also clearly defined. The management also needs to be adequate in providing the resources needed by the employees to be in a position to conduct their daily business operations. Supervision is also another factor and it should be easily accessible to all the individuals in the company. The superiors are expected to act in a competent and fair manner to all the employees, failure to do so leads to frustration at work. Interpersonal relations are also paramount at the workplace, creating good working relations between the superiors, subordinates and colleagues should be constantly encouraged so as to have a quality collective life at work (Adair 2004).

Salary or money is another hygiene factor that Herzberg argues could lead to dissatisfaction if not gotten in pertinent amounts. It is also not seen as long term potential satisfier due to its short-term feeling impact (Axelsson, Bokedal 2009). Other hygiene factors include status which could be symbolized in a person's rank, title or even the size of the office. Job security is also vital as it gives an assurance to the employees that they are safe from losing their position in the company or even employment all-together. Moreover the working conditions are quite crucial if they employees are to feel satisfied working in an organization. It does not mean that the top managers only concentrate on the physical aspect of the work but also the amount of work distributed to each individual and also provide enough facilities for the workers to conduct their daily operations. Last but not least the personal life of the employee is also a hygiene factor, being that the employee spends most of the time at work it should have a good reflection on his life and family life if satisfaction is to be expected e.g. working too much could be a source of stress to the employee and even the people close to him (Adair 2004).

The Motivator factors could be characterized as a set of intrinsic factors whose presence builds upon motivation thus leading to high levels of performance. If these conditions are not present they don't necessarily lead to dissatisfaction rather they are more related to the job content. They include achievement specific to success of a completion of a job or creating new solutions to problems. Recognition is also another way to motivate employees, any act of recognition boosts the energy of the employees because they feel that their efforts are not going unrecognized. In addition providing possibilities of growth at the work place also has a positive influence on the employees' motivation as it allows them to develop personally and also professionally. Advancement is by the same token a motivator as it provides channels of change by enhancing positions at the workplace. Employees don't want to feel like they are stuck doing the same job for a long duration of time as it may lead to too much monotony. Furthermore allocating responsibility roles has a great impact on motivation especially when it's matched up with significant jurisdiction to discharge it. Last but not least the work itself should be motivating enough for the workers. By being involved in doing the actual work it should be enjoyable and exciting despite the different phases that may accompany it (Adair 2004).

To sum up it all it is correct to say that the hygiene factors are almost similar to those of Maslow's lower- level of need i.e. physiological, safety and social needs. In reality their presence is to prevent anything that could result in dissatisfaction

while their absence only leads to high levels of dissatisfaction. They however do not lead to motivation of individuals which could accompany good performance. On the other hand the motivators are equivalent to the Maslow's higher-level of needs which are regarded as job content factors that prompt people to accomplish. Herzberg's argument is that only these type of motivators can stimulate motivated behavior (Szilagyi et al. 1990).

Top managers can also implement this theory in the organization through focusing on satisfying the Herzberg motivators and avoiding problems with the hygiene factors. Individual job satisfaction in the companies can only be reached if the top management finds out what really contributes to job enrichment and empowerment thus improving the overall performance of the organization (Adair 2004).

Alderfer's ERG Theory

The Alderfer's ERG theory of needs was proposed by Clayton Alderfer and his purpose was to establish a relationship between the human needs in an organizational setting. His theory summarizes that of Maslow's but in three need categories namely (E) existence (R) relatedness (G) growth. Figure 3 below best describes how the three are related.

Figure 3. Alderfer's ERG Theory

The existence needs are represented by all the various forms of physiological material needs and desires, they could be hunger, shelter and thirst. From an organization context they symbolize the needs of pay and good working conditions more so they are similar to those of Maslow's physiological and certain safety needs. Relatedness on the other hand represents the interpersonal relationships formed at the workplace. This need heavily relies on the process of sharing feelings with fellow workmates so as to achieve satisfaction.

The Maslow's safety, social and some of the self-esteem/ego needs are analogous to Alderfer's relatedness need. Finally the growth need is representative of a person's endeavors towards visionary and innovative personal advancement on the job. Satisfaction of the growth needs can only be reached if the individual taps into his skills and capabilities and maximizes them fully. Developing on new competences also allows the individual to garner new skills as he progresses on the ones that he already has (Szilagyi, et al. 1990).

The ERG theory has been based upon three major propositions, in that the less each level of need is satisfied the more likely it will be desired e.g. if pay needs are neglected by the top management the more they will be desired by the staff.

As for the lower level of needs the more satisfaction is awarded to them the more the likelihood of a greater desire towards the relatedness e.g. if the needs of an individual have been fully satisfied in terms of good pay the more he will gear towards fostering good and long lasting interpersonal relations at the enterprise. Lastly if the high level of needs are ignored the more the lower needs are yearned for i.e. if the staff's growth needs are not well catered for, the more aspirations they will have towards nurturing satisfactory interpersonal relations with their fellow colleagues. The ERG model bases its findings on how people should progress up the hierarchy and also shows a regression down the hierarchy when people fail to pay attention on the higher needs. This is something that the Maslow's pyramid fails to indicate the theory only demonstrates on how one should progress to the next level (McShane, Glinow 2010).

The managers have the responsibility of ensuring that they recognize that employees have an assorted array of needs which must be satisfied in a synchronous manner. Placing too much attention on one level of needs means that there will be some weaknesses on the other levels thus a reverting kind of an effect which in most cases leads to frustration. In other words this is known as the frustration-

regression principle which is evident when the higher level of needs remains unfulfilled the impulse is to go back to the lower level needs which seem effortless to satisfy. For effective motivation in the company, ERG theory is only efficient if all the three levels are given the same attention simultaneously. The management should also be at the fore front of perceiving these conditions early so that the necessary steps can be taken to cater for the needs which are frustrated in order to aid the employees to seek growth again (Szilagyi et al. 1990).

McClelland's Theory of Needs

David McClelland is another psychologist whose theory of needs went on to further explore the idea of a need's strength being altered through social influences. McClelland's theory was quite particular as emphasis was placed more on how a need could be strengthened through reinforcement, learning and social conditions. Through these standpoint views he was able to come up with three learned needs namely: Achievement, affiliation and power (McShane et al. 2010).

According to McShane the need of achievement which is abbreviated as (nAch) is an urge that makes people want to attain goals that are equitable, reasonable and at the same time don't require explicit feedback or recognition once they succeed. Such people prefer working individually rather than in groups and the kind of task they take are neither to easy or complex to finish. Individuals with high-nAch tend not to put so much emphasis on recognition that is too obvious after succeeding in a task. To them money is not so important in regards to motivating them unless used for recognition or feedback purposes. On the contrary low nAch employees perform better at tasks when money is used as a stimulus because they know succeeding at an assignment will be rewarded (McShane et al. 2010).

Need for affiliation which is abbreviated as (nAff) is defined as a need in which people constantly pursue ratification from others while trying to avoid conflict and disputes. They are able to achieve through conforming to other peoples' standards and expectations so as to portray a favourable appearance. Employees with high nAff tend to be good at sales positions as this kind of work demands one to foster long lasting relationships in order to sell the products or services. In case of conflicts at the work place they are good at working out the disputes and encourage others to get along.

The downfall to these kind of people is that when faced with adversity and given the responsibility to allocate scarce resources, they tend to be less efficacious, this is because they want to ensure everyone is happy which is impossible. In the end they end up creating more conflict with the decision they make. From an organization point of view managers should delegate the tasks of decision making to people who have low nAff thus a lower need of personal approval to avoid any unfairness or bias (McShane et al. 2010).

To conclude the McClelland's theory of needs is the need for power better abbreviated as (nPow). This refers to a need whereby an individual wants to always control his surroundings, tangible resources available, and even people for his beneficial purposes or power gain. Such individuals are ever eager to take up leadership positions and are more interested in maintaining these posts. During meetings they always want to give suggestions on how business operations should be run and are keen to evaluate situations. McClelland pinpointed that there are two types of powers: first personalized power which is more aligned to an individual's personal interest, i.e. the person is more interested on what the new power he has can benefit him and is likely to show it off to others as a prestige symbol.

The second type of power is the socialized power in which individuals have a higher need for power in order they can assist others. The corporations of today's world should encourage top leaders to work more on having socialized power rather than personalized power. Effective leaders are the ones who have a high degree of altruism keeping in mind that their social responsibility is to ensure that the actions they undertake affects them and others too. The repercussions of their actions will be felt not only by them but also those they are leading (McShane et al. 2010).

Process Theories

The process theories are more focused on what energizes motivational behaviour and also the direction this behaviour takes. The process theories go deeper to look at the desired end result as an aim towards motivational behaviour. Some of the process theories are expectancy theory, equity theory, goal theory and reinforcement theory. Additionally the four drive theory and the Mc-Gregory theory X and Y will be discussed

Expectancy Theory

Vroom's expectancy theory first appeared in his doctoral dissertation Vroom 1960. He later expanded his theory to cover work motivation in 1964 in which he suggests that people usually prefer some goals or outcomes over others. He further went on to recommend that once a preferred outcome was achieved the reaction would be satisfaction. Vroom's expectancy model was based upon three concepts of value, expectancy and force.

His assumption was that the choices made by people during a certain course of action is based duly on psychological events that may occur jointly with their behaviour. In this theory the force concept is equated to motivation. Using an algebraic expression the products of valences multiplied by expectancies results to motivation: Motivation (Force) = Valence X Expectancy (Niraj 2009, 169).

McShane equates the expectancy theory to a platform in which through experience an individual can develop expectations in which job performance levels can be achieved. He further states that the development of job performance and work behaviours expectations can lead to certain outcomes thus more effort can be exerted towards achieving these outcomes so that they may lead to the fulfilment of our needs. The expectancy theory is presented in Figure 4 below to expound more on how it works (McShane et al. 2003).

The expectancy theory bases its assumption that motivation is based upon three main elements. The first is the effort – performance expectation which means if it is increased it may lead to good performance thus in other words can be referred to as expectancy. The second fundamental is the performance – outcome performance perception whereby good performance will eventually lead to certain outcomes or rewards, it can also be attributed as instrumentality. The third element is the valence which is the value or allure placed on a reward or outcome to an individual. Consequently for an individual to be motivated, the end result of the outcome or reward has to be highly valued by the person. The belief has to be that any additional effort will be a precedence to higher performance and higher performance will in the end result to bigger rewards or outcomes (Bowditch, Buono 2001).

Employee motivation is very important and the management has to keep in mind that all the three components mentioned above influence it in one or another. If any of them is neglected it will definitely have a negative reaction thus a decline in motivation. For this reason managers need to understand what each level entails: the first being effort-to-performance expectancy (E-P) is defined as perceived prospect by an individual that his effort will precede a particular level of performance. The expectancy is illustrated as a probability ranging from 0.0 to 1.0. In some cases, employees may have absolute confidence that they can effortlessly achieve the task given to them thus a probability of 1.0. In other scenarios, even with the highest levels of effort they may be unable to accomplish an assignment thus a probability of 0.0. Often the E-P falls between these two extremes. E.g. an employee may not feel so motivated to do something that he knows even with his array of skills he won't accomplish it (McShane et al. 2003).

Performance to outcome expectancy (P-O) is the second element and it can be characterized as perceived probability that definitive conduct or performance levels results to clear cut outcomes. The probability is 1.0 when employees have the belief that achieving a certain task will result in a particular outcome. Further-more they may also believe that despite their successful performance, the influence on the outcome is ineffective thus a probability of 0.0. Constantly the P-O falls in between these two extremes. Outcomes could be numerous hence we cannot evaluate them all but we can keep a close eye to those that interests us. Therefore it is significant to note that only those outcomes that we value and interests us are the driving force for our motivation behaviour.

The term valence represent feelings that may emanate from specific outcomes. In simple terms it is also referred to as forecasted feelings of satisfaction or dissatisfaction by an individual towards an outcome (McShane et al. 2003). The outcomes may acquire valences on their own right as they may be regarded to lead to outcomes projected to be sources of either satisfaction or dissatisfaction. E.g. an employee who accumulates a lot of earnings might feel satisfied because he has a lot of money in the bank, alternatively for another accruing a lot of earnings may be due to the desire of wanting to own an expensive car or apartment (Miner 2006).

The valences are regarded as strengths of a person's preferences towards particular outcomes. Valences could also be referred to as the value a person places upon issues like increase in pay, recognition, accolades, promotions etc. Valences can have negative or positive impacts in a work situation. The actual range isn't of essence as it may range from -1 to +1 or from -100 to +100. The expectation would be that a hike in salaries would have a positive valence while supervisory censures may end up leading to a negative valence. In this case the negative valences are not highly valued by employees (Szilagyi, et al. 1990, 124).

The expectancy theory model has an advantage in that it provides a clear framework on how motivation works. By using the model the goal is to have well motivated employees and this can be only be accomplished if all the three fundamentals are increased simultaneously. To increase the E-P expectancies the main goal is to make the employees have complete belief in themselves that they are qualified to execute their jobs in a successful manner. The top management hence need to ensure they recruit people with the skills they are looking for and then properly train them, and thereafter provide them with clear cut instructions on what the job entails. In addition appointing lesser tasks to the newly recruited will help them master what is required of them providing they are given enough time and the essential resources to complete their duties. Finally counselling and coaching services are vital especially for those employees whom may feel they are lacking self-confidence. This can be achieved by bringing aboard similar employees who were able to successfully complete work assignments to help boost their colleagues' self-esteem (McShane et al. 2003).

The P-O expectancies can be improved by accurately measuring the employee's performance and giving credit where it is due. The more valued rewards should be awarded to those who have higher job performances.

The process is not always clear as most companies may find easy to give accolades to those who have performed well while ignoring poor performers because they don't want to create conflict with them. Organizations should however keep in mind that the aim is to raise the belief that the better an employee performs the higher the value of a certain outcome. Additionally the outcomes should be clearly expounded that their results will be of successful performance and the rewards given will be based on the employees past achievements. Likewise giving good examples of employees who were able to attain high levels of performance and were awarded high rewards will give a positive ambition to others to aspire to be higher performers at the workplace (McShane et al. 2003).

Finally the outcomes or rewards must be desired by the individuals for them to feel motivated. Managers need to take into account the core valence or outcomes their employees want rather than making assumptions (Bowditch et al. 2001). Instead they can ensure an even distribution of rewards which are valued by the employees as well as putting in place reward systems that individualize the awards so that the workers can have a diversified display of choices to choose from (McShane et al. 2003).

Adam's Equity Theory

The equity theory came into existence after it was developed and tested by John Stacey Adam in 1963. The fundamental behind this process theory is to explain the different perceptions that could developed by different individuals when it comes to distribution and exchange of resources. To further break it down, it basically means what motivates employees to take certain actions when they feel they are being treated inequitably (McShane et al. 2003). The notion behind this theory shows why the employees may end up being de-motivated in their affiliation towards their job or employer when they feel as if theory inputs are larger compared to the end result of the outputs. For a better understanding the Figure below shows the Adam's Equity theory and what it entails.

Adams' Equity Theory diagram - job motivation

Figure 5. Adam's Equity Theory of job motivation

To clearly understand this theory, it is important to look at the four elements that sum up the equity theory, which are: outcome/input ratio, comparison other, equity evaluation and finally consequences of inequity. The outcome/input ratio is essentially the value of outcomes an employee receives divided by value of inputs he or she provides in the exchange of relationship. Inputs could range from skills and abilities that an employee has to effort, experience and employee alternative contributions to the company. On the contrary outcome is what the company gives the employees in exchange of their inputs, which could be pay bonuses, promotions, awards and recognition. Being that employees receive a lot of outcomes in a workplace it may be difficult to determine the overall values. Moreover the inputs and outcomes may possess different value and importance from one individual to the next thus the variations of these two cannot be generalised (McShane et al. 2003).

The second element is the comparison of other in which the theory states that often individuals compare their situations with that of another comparison. Equity's theory has not clearly identified what exactly is the comparison of other therefore it could range from anything like a person, a crowd of people or even oneself in the past.

It could also be another job or company or even a person in a similar job. In a work setting employees holding senior ranks are likely to compare themselves with their correspondents from other firms. Chief executives also tend to do the same since they don't have direct comparison within the confines of the organization they are working for (McShane et al. 2003).

The equity evaluation is the third element and this can be determined by comparing the outcome/input ratio to that of comparison other's ratio. By doing so people are able to develop either feelings of equity or inequity. Equity evaluation can become complex from one individual to another especially when the comparison of other has different outcomes and inputs. With the equity evaluation chances of under-reward inequity situations occurring are quite common, and this is represented when for example in a company some employees find out that they are being under-paid while their colleagues are getting slightly a higher pay than them even though their tasks are similar and also the effort exerted to these task is also the same. Over-reward inequity is also another equity evaluation condition in which the common belief amongst a certain group of employees is that their ratio of outcome/inputs is greater than the comparison other's ratio. Notwithstanding over-reward is not as

common as under-reward considering that humans generally adjust their concepts so as to validate affirmative results (McShane et al. 2010).

Lastly the consequences of inequity is primarily the pressure that arises in the event of people observing inclinations of inequity. The higher this pressure is the more motivated employees become in taking steps to rid of the inequity. McShane talks of seven significant ways to reduce the feeling of inequality in the workplace: which are reducing the inputs and this could be achieved through slow performance of work tasks given or even less involvement in the organizational company objectives. The second one is increase of the outcomes which could be accomplished through asking of a pay rise directly or even through a labour union. Thirdly employees could increase the comparison other's inputs by asking those co-workers who are receiving higher pay to justify their outcome by doing a larger amount of work. Fourthly reducing the comparison other's inputs is also another way to diminish inequity conditions and this can be done by placing suggestions to have co-workers pay which is high to be cut. Fifth, employees could change perceptions and believe that their colleagues who are receiving higher pay are doing what's required of them to deserve such kind of pay.

Changing the comparison of other is the sixth way to thwart feelings of under-reward inequity and it can be achieved through comparing oneself with someone who is in the same situation as yourself or maybe closer, it could be that the tasks being undertaken are the same or the paygrade is the same. Finally the most extreme response to inequity would be to leave unfavourable working fields. The employee does this to avoid the inequity either by moving to another work station so as to avoid his fellow workers who are being over-paid. Feigning sickness in order to have more sick leave days is also another way to avoid working and in extreme cases an employee may end up quitting the job because they don't want to be in an environment where they feel they are being treated unequally (McShane et al. 2010). All these are capable of balancing out the unequal conditions that the employees might be experiencing amongst themselves. The correlation between inequity and employee motivation is quite inseparable, this is because any awareness of inequity like conditions are likely to lead to negative emotions, and emotions are the drivers behind motivation hence demotivation type of reaction is expected any time negative emotions arise.

Goal Setting Theory

In the 1960s Edwin Locke came up with a motivational theory termed Goal Setting in which he stated that there was a link between task performance and goal setting. By having challenging goals in the company accompanied with the appropriate channels of feedback, higher and better task performance is realized. I.e. Goals tend to direct the employees to the paths of what needs to be done and the amount of effort required to achieve the task given. Many organizations around the world have realized that by implementing the goal setting approach in their daily routines they are able to efficiently motivate their employees as it is one of the most effective theories of motivation (McShane et al. 2003, 150).

For a better understanding of the theory it is important we first of all comprehend what goals are and the process of goal setting. Goals can be defined as critical objectives that employees try to attain from their job effort. The process of goal setting is illustrated as a course of action taken to motivate employees through interpreting their role concepts and enacting performance objectives. Employee performance has the potential of being improved through goal setting in the following main ways: by extending the vigor and persistence placed on effort and also through providing the workers with role perceptions that are clear so that any effort they exert is channeled towards habits that will lead to a progression of their work conduct (McShane et al. 2003).

Some of the organizations apply goal setting through a formal process called management by objectives abbreviated as (MBO).

Generally this process involves identifying policies aspired by an organization which then are circulated to work departments and individual employees. The progression of the goals is also monitored through MBO. Goal setting is quite complicated and it is for this reason specific conditions have been identified in order to ensure maximum job effort and performance. The specific conditions are as follows: specific goals, relevant goals, challenging goals, goal commitment, participation in goal formation and goal feedback (McShane et al. 2003, 151).

Top management should give goals that are specific and clear as employees are most likely to invest much effort rather on targets that expect them to do the best they can to attain the given goals. Through clarifying what the employees are expected to do, it means that the communication of the kind of performance expected is clear and precise. This means any loopholes of misunderstanding are eliminated and greater output and performance is realized.

Goals also have to be relevant and connected to an individual's job which is within the control of his work e.g. a goal which aims at waste reduction has to also be combined with the production process otherwise it won't be valued by the employee if his control is limited in the early stages of production (McShane et al. 2010). Moreover the goals have to be challenging in nature this because there is a sense of pride and triumph when an individual finally achieves that goal. This in a way fulfils the growth needs of achievement which are regarded as high level of needs. Organizations should therefore set goals that will challenge the employees to get out of their comfort zone and maximize their potential by activating their knowledge and skills required to attain a particular goal. However learning goals should also be incorporated at the beginning of new and difficult tasks as it is more effective than dwelling on goals of performance outcome (Clegg et al. 2008, 922).

Goal commitment is another important aspect of goal setting theory as it reflects the value of commitment placed on a certain goal with the conviction that it is significant, attainable and at least approachable (Clegg et al. 2008, 923). It is crucial to note that there is a limit to goals that are challenging and sometimes when very difficult goals are set, employees may end up losing interest and commitment to attain them.

This can be equated to the expectancy theory mentioned earlier whereby lower E – P expectancy means that the expectation of the goal to be achieved is quite low thus motivation towards the goal commitment by the employee will decline (McShane et al. 2010).

Goal participation basically means involving employees in processes of goal setting and other decision making process that affect them. When supervisors allow their employees to be practically involved in making the goals they ultimately improve the potential of goal commitment as employees feel they have a sense of ownership unlike if the goals were set without their involvement. The workforce of this day and age is progressively expecting to be involved in such processes because it is important for them to have a voice when policies regarding their well-being are being formed. The quality of the goals is also improved because employees may have valuable suggestions that maybe unknown to those originally making the goals (McShane et al. 2003).

Finally goal feedback is vital process in goal setting because people require feedback so as to document their progress as far as their goals are concerned (Clegg et al. 2008, 923). Feedback is also a crucial part of motivation as the higher level of needs like achievement cannot be fully contented if there are no channels of giving information once a goal is accomplished (McShane et al. 2003).

To give feedback effectively it should have some elements attached to it. These elements are: the feedback should be specific and relevant, particularly it should pinpoint the exact metrics and also the individual behavior that led to a certain outcome. E.g. a sales manager could acknowledge an individual's effort, that in the last two months the customer base increased by three percent due to the diligence and persistence work effort. The feedback should also be timely soon as results are realized so that the employees can be able to determine the actions they partook and the overall consequences' that came afterwards. Moreover it is critical to give frequently give sufficient feedback depending on the employee's knowledge regarding the task at hand and also the duration that the task will take to be completed. Last but not least employees can only be motivated by feedback that comes from authentic and credible sources (McShane et al. 2010).

Goal setting can be summarized as one of the theories in organizational behavior that have been tested and remained valid since its inception.

As we have discussed earlier goal setting combined with feedback is an effective channel of improving employee performance and motivation. Nonetheless it is essential to note that the practicality of goal setting in the organizations can lead to some problems. One of the problems is that some of the dimensions of job performance cannot quite be measured as they are complex and are associated with long term performances outcomes.

This is because the goal setting process is focused more on short term goals rather than long term goals. Hence jobs that require long durations to get completed may end up not being properly measured. The second complication is that when goals are bound with monetary incentives employees tend to prefer easy goals than the challenging ones. At the same time they claim the easy goals are quite complex to achieve so that they can pocket the extra bonuses. Finally those establishments that are already using the goal setting approach are always effective however the problem comes in when new and complex job assignments are introduced. It is for this reason that when intense learning processes are ongoing, goal setting should not be combined together with such as it may not be applicable (McShane et al. 2010).

Reinforcement Theory

The foundation of reinforcement theory was first laid in 1911 by Edward Thorndike in which he explained what the law of effect was. His findings were that behaviors that led to positive outcomes had a likelihood of being repeated while those that led to negative outcomes were not likely repeated. The implications of the law of effect in a workplace would be that any kind of behavior that would seem like it was reinforced either through rewards by the management would have a tendency to be repeated while those that are not would end up being done away with (Niraj 2009).

B.F skinner later came up with the operant conditioning and it states that human behavior is regulated and controlled by the environment surrounding an individual (Bowditch et al. 2001). His basic assumption is also based on Thorndike's earlier work of law of effect. Skinner 1953 suggested that employee's behaviours that led to positive outcomes were to be repeated and those behaviours that led to negative outcomes should not be repeated. This theory places a lot of its emphasis on what happens to an individual once he or she takes a certain action thus the inner drives of individuals are ignored by this theory as it overlooks the inner state of the individual. For this theory to be effective Skinner highlights that organizations role is to ensure that the external work setting is designed in a way that will effectively motivate the employees.

Reinforcement theory underlines four basic techniques that could be used to modify employee behaviour and even boost their motivation. These approaches are positive reinforcement, negative reinforcement, punishment and extinction.

The positive reinforcement is a technique based upon evoking and enhancing new behaviours through the addition of rewards and incentives without the elimination of the benefits.

Organizations can be able to achieve this by introducing fringe benefits like promotions slots and even pay bonuses at the workplace. Positive reinforcement could also be intangible in this case recognition by the employer, e.g. an employer could easily give an employee a pat on the back for successfully handling a difficult customer (Niraj 2009). This type of reinforcement has been discussed by many reinforcement scholars as the most effective channel to sustain desirable behaviour (Bowditch et al. 2001). However the negative reinforcement is equally as important if any desirable behaviours are to be repeated. By avoiding actions that could lead to negative consequences the likelihood of having what's considered to be good behaviour in a workplace being repeated is quite high. This can be portrayed in the following example if an employee comes late to work two days consecutively and gets scolded for doing so, if by the third day he is able to show up in time the supervisor should not reprimand him. By doing so it will encourage the employee to try and keep time in the near future since he would like to avoid the repercussions that come accompany lateness (Niraj 2009).

Punishment reinforcement is another approach that aims at removing any unwanted behaviour. The main focus with this approach is to discourage those type of habits that are not supposed to be repeated. This approach is seen as a straight forward method of curbing bad behaviour as it is not difficult for the employees to understand when they are being punished for wrong-doing (Bowditch et al. 2001). A recent study on punctuality indicated that employees who were fined for being late to work tended to be more effective in the daily duties. The study further indicated that paying of fines to co-workers was a good tactic in improving the employee attendance as many of the workers would rather pay the fines to the employer than their own colleagues (Siang 2012).

In conclusion managers are expected to find out and implement strategically the appropriate approach in order to either elicit or eliminate certain behaviours in a workplace. As we examined earlier the positive reinforcement seems to be the best method in encouraging and motivating employees to perform better in their delegated tasks. Employees who are always encouraged to do better tend to have desirable behaviour as they already know that positive rewards await them. Moreover punishment reinforcement seems to work when negative habits are to be eliminated as employees who are penalized tend to show better discipline, however it should be enforced with caution as too much of it may end up being counterproductive and cause a decrease in the morale of workers thus demotivating them (Wei, Yazdanifard, 2014).

Four Drive Theory

The four drive theory was developed by Paul Lawrence and Nitin Nohria who are professors at Harvard business school. In this theory they both state that everyone has an intuitive drive to acquire, bond, learn and defend whilst incorporating emotions and rationality.

The first drive is drive to acquire and its best described as a spur to seek, take, control and hold on to objects and personal experiences. The drive to acquire is not only about getting basic needs like food and water but also consists of self-concepts like being recognized in the society through prestigious status. The second drive is drive to bond whereby individuals tend to form social relations and foster mutual commitments with other people. It is the reason as to why people will connect with distinct social groups that have the same mindsets as them. Bonding tends to motivate people to work in cooperation with others hence it is an integral part of any organization if any success or progress is expected. The third drive is the drive to learn and this is characterized as the drive that makes us as individuals to want to satisfy the curiosity within us so as to better understand ourselves and the surroundings we are in. There is always that information gap within us that yearns to be filled especially when we are observing something that may appear erratic or is not in the confines of our current knowledge. Just as Maslow's self-actualization growth needs the drive to learn is also classified in the same level. Last but not least is the drive to defend and safeguard ourselves both socially and physically. The drive to defend is quite symbolic to the response fight or flight when exposed to a crisis. It is not only about protecting ourselves physically but also the relationships we have forged with others, the belief systems as well as what we acquired financially (McShane et al. 2010).

The Four drives are all internal and universal thus they are found in the brains of all human beings. All of them are independent of one another thus no hierarchy is present neither is one drive superior or inferior to the other. Three of the drives however are constantly proactive and only the drive to defend is reactive as it is triggered by threat. Four-drive theory has a holistic approach as there is a relation between all the drives and also a humanistic approach since it relies on the role of social impact and human thought and not just intuition (McShane et al. 2010).

In an organization setting this theory is recommended so as to establish a platform in which the work setting provides a uniform space whereby all the drives can be fulfilled in a balanced manner. This means that employees can only feel motivated if they are provided with the best workplaces that are accompanied with conditions that will help them accomplish all the four drives. The management can achieve this by implementing reward systems, opportunities for learning in order to foster growth as well as social interactions avenues so that staff can connect with each other. It is also critical to have a balance among all the drives when fulfilling the four drives. Organizations are advised not to put too much or too little attention when trying to fulfil each drive. This is because as mentioned earlier all the four work together harmoniously and dependently with each other e.g. if a company encourages the drive to acquire and neglects the drive to bond chances are that in the long run the cases of disputes and rampant behaviour among the employees will be frequent. Moreover constant change in the company might lead to the drive to learn however too much of it may provoke the drive to defend to the degree of the workers becoming defensive and territorial as they resist any chances of further changes. Thus organizations should ensure they give enough opportunities for all the drives to be fulfilled in a harmonious manner (McShane et al. 2010).

McGregor's Theory X and Theory Y

Theory X and theory Y was created and developed by a man known as Douglas McGregor in the 1960s during his time at MIT Sloan School of management. These two theories describe the kind of attitudes employees have in relation to workforce motivation and have been put into use by many organizations around the globe. McGregor's proposition is that most managers usually base their assumptions about people on either one of his two theories, theory X or theory Y (Tyson 2015). According to McGregor theory X basic

hypothesis is that people are passive and uninterested and sometimes resistant to organizational needs unless there is active interference by the top management. This is due to the nature of an average man being unambitious, indolent and inherently self-centered and will try and avoid responsibility at all costs. He however points out that this kind of behavior is not an effect of man's innate nature rather an outcome of management philosophy and practice (Latham 2007).

Theory X can be examined from a traditional point of view whereby the main incentive is constant supervision which is necessary for the theory to be effective in an organizational setting. Hence the managerial approach in regards to employee motivation highly emphasizes total control of the employees from the higher level of managers to their subordinates because it is all about the pain and fear (Stewart 2010). It is for this reason that McGregor states that people end up adopting defensive postures because they want to group up and beat the system with any chance they get. Already the management expects such results from them hence when they do react this way it comes with no surprise (Tyson 2015).

Some of the assumptions managers bestow upon their employees when theory X is in question is that due to people having a dislike nature towards work they tend to avoid it. The employees also lack a sense of responsibility thus very little ambition and above all coercion and sense of control has to be established by the managers to get people to do their work. In most cases threats of punishment is also used so as to pass a message to the workers that there will be harsh consequences if they don't meet their end of the bargain as far as work is concerned. The underlying element of this theory can be concluded to base its belief on the negative aspects of people as a motivational technique because the managers have to motivate their junior staff members with pessimistic approaches like punishment, aggression, controlling and coercion to get their duties done. It is paramount to note that theory X is mostly suitable in governmental or public sector organizations where people's trust is quite questionable. Unlike the government offices, the private organization sector cannot apply this theory since the assumption is that they promote freedom and autonomy and also people are more likely to be trusted (Rao, Kumar, Tej 2010).

Theory Y on the contrary is more aligned towards the positive aspects of people. According to Stewart, human beings are seen as active comparatively to being passive shapers of their own selves and their surroundings. The proper way to manage such people is to supervise as little as possible and give them space to thrive on their own ((Stewart 2010). Some of the assumptions regarding theory Y is that people relate the nature of working to that of play or rest and in most cases they aspire to exercise self-direction and self-control especially if they are committed to the organizational objectives. In addition

the average person is capable of learning to accept or pursue responsibility as well as shun laziness. In fact they have become diligent due to the consequences they have experienced when they tried to be languorous (Rao et al. 2010).

This theory further states that under the appropriate conditions people have the potential to be creative and innovative and apply such applications to their workplace. Since the private organizations are more inclined towards performance rather than procedure this theory is mostly applicable in the private sector. Employees in such organizations are motivated through creation of techniques that lead to job enrichment. Additionally they have ample freedom to decide on their work, which activities to partake in as well as making their own decisions which would lead to organizational performance (Rao et al. 2010).

In conclusion Stewart portrays how theory X is viewed in today's corporate world, almost as that of a state of conflict. In World X managers come across as eyeing every single step taken by their subordinates during daily operations due to the magnitude of mistrust present. The number of employees who may be eager to call out their bosses due to their autocratic approaches of leading is quite few, and often not so many managers are enthusiastic with identifying with the idea of being harsh or mistreating their junior colleagues. On the other hand theory Y is seen as a peaceful state in which both the managers and workers are in total agreement and embrace each other as they pursue the journey towards empowerment and personal fulfilment. The vision according theory Y is that freedom and self-realization propagates tremendous productivity (Stewart 2010).

PERFORMANCE AND MOTIVATION

The Link between Performance and Motivation

Since the beginning of time business leaders have always strived in sustaining good work performance in their organisations. In a world that is full of competition working hard is no longer enough, employees have to perform better and in a continuous manner lest the competitors catch up with them. It is therefore correct to say that motivation and performance work hand in hand and they are both important factors for the workforce of a company (Stredwick 2002). Having noted that these two are connected it is important to understand what performance means and exactly what does it entail.

Performance is a complex concept and it can be interpreted in a lot of different ways (Hutchinson 2013). Greene states that the definition of performance can be in terms of results, behaviours or both. He further argues that when measuring results in a quantitative manner there are some advantages that accompany this e.g. the subjectivity required is reduced. However it is important to note that not all jobs can use these quantitative measures because in some cases what can be counted may not hold any significance as what may be judged subjectively. On the other hand the behavioural measures when performance is concerned is suitable for most job if not all. However measuring behaviours have been on the receiving end of criticism because of the subjectivity involved with it (Greene 2011).

Hutchinson further adds that performance can be defined simply by the outputs or achievements which have been pre-set by certain objectives or the units that have been produced. She however states that this type of definition has some limitations as it disregards the factors that are outside the control of an individual that may end up having an impact on the performance realized i.e. there is no explanation of the 'how' of the performance. Alternatively just as Greene asserts that performance is also about the behaviours of an individual, Hutchinson also affirms that focus could also be pointed toward employees behaviours or actions as a way to understand what performance is all about (Hutchinson 2013).

There are many definitions for performance management depending on what context it is used. Some relate performance management to a formal performance appraisal process while others see it as a way to measure the performance in an organization or the pay that is awarded once a certain level of performance has been achieved (Hutchinson 2013).

Dessler defines performance management as a process in which companies make sure that employees are working towards achieving the organizational goals of the company. Managers are expected to define the employee's goals and work, develop the skills and capabilities of the workers and then conduct an evaluation of the person's goal-directed behaviour so as to properly reward the individual in a manner that is coherent with the person's and the company's needs (Dessler 2009). It is important to note that with performance management, how performance is defined should be in a way that is apt with the organization's context as well as the set objectives of the company. The company should also be in a position to measure results and compare the actual results to what is expected or required.

Furthermore when defining performance it should be in a manner that is fair to all employees or other parties involved. This is because performance management is deemed as an important element of the psychological contract entered into between the employer and his employees. In the event that the employer defines performance in a criterion that is unacceptable to the employees or maybe the set goals by the employer seem unreasonable to achieve by the employees, conflict is likely to arise. This kind of conflict could have a negative impact on the employees and reduce their motivation in accomplishing the organization's expectations. In conclusion it is imperative for organizations to ensure that they define and manage performance in a mutual aggregable manner so as to generate more employee commitment and motivation towards performing better in the objectives of the company (Greene 2011).

There is a significant connection between some of the theories that were discussed in chapter 2. The goal setting theory has close affiliation to the performance management concept. Locke pinpoints conditions that are necessary in order for the goals to be effective and induce motivation like behaviour and at the same time influence performance. Some of these conditions suggested are that goals should be clear cut and challenging. Research suggests that companies which present specific challenging goals often translate into better performance than those do your best kind of goals. When goals are ambiguous chances are they will not fully communicate the intended purpose. Those in charge of setting the goals should carefully scrutinize the goals they have set in order to remove any confusion that may be accompanied by having vague goals. In addition, the set goals should be attainable, when individuals feel that they cannot be able to achieve what has been set by the management because they term it as difficult, it is highly likely they will end up being demotivated thus reducing the level of performance. The most common factor that is responsible for individuals feeling incapable of achieving the expectations set upon them, is that they lack the adequate skills and the know-how required. Organizations should therefore ensure that their employees have enough resources to train, learn and develop their skills so that they are able to be in a position to achieve the set expectations. Last but not least feedback is also another important element of the goal setting theory. Feedback should be provided in a prompt and precise manner to the employees. This allows management to communicate to their workers if they are performing well or not. It also provides an open forum to exchange ideas and suggestions on how to improve on areas that performance may be poor. It is worthwhile to also note that Equity theory has some

valuable contributions to performance. The theory revolves around how feelings of inequity or equity may be formed based upon what people perceive to be fair or unfair. The more the pressure on what is perceived unfair the more motivated an individual becomes to want to take action so as to reinstate equity. E.g. an employee who perceives that the salary he or she receives is lower than the other co-workers, the more this individual is likely to reduce the effort on his or her job. This will have negative effect on the overall performance as it will lead to poor performance and the person may not be willing to co-operate because they feel they are being treated unfairly. The motivation will also be affected in a negative way. On the contrary the employees who discern that they are being over-rewarded will want to maintain the status of being over-rewarded. They will work an extra mile to ensure that they do not lose the equity being awarded to them. The motivation for such individuals is definitely high are more likely to be perform better at their tasks (Hutchinson 2013).

Consequently from the above discussion, it is correct to infer that there is a connection between motivation and performance. The focus point however is to understand that there is a differentiating factor between motivation and behaviour when performance is involved. Motivation itself is a psychological state and the outcome of motivation is the behaviour. Only through taking action does motivation truly become connected to performance (Kurose 2013). The common belief has been that, highly motivated people always deliver a better job performance but it is important to note that performance is not only dependent on motivation. There are other key factors like ability and skills as well as opportunities to participate that contribute to performance as demonstrated in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. The AMO model of performance adapted from Appelbaum 2000 (Hutchinson, 2013).

The AMO model of performance represents A (ability), M (motivation) and O (opportunity) a framework initially proposed by Bailey in 1993 then later developed by Appelbaum in 2000. This model has become worldwide accepted as a way to show how the HR policies can work and influence performance. The proposition of this model is that HR practices reinforces on improved employee performance through the development of employees abilities to carry out their tasks at the same time promotes employees motivation for their discretionary effort. This ensures that the workers have the opportunity to completely utilize their skills and be motivated. A good example on how the HR policies can achieve the proposed goals and even influence performance through the AMO model is: A (ability) is something that is determined in the early stages of selection and recruitment, and this is achieved by evaluating the capabilities of employees recruited so as to select the ones' having the right competencies. Training and development is also crucial in that it allows the employees to garner new knowledge and skills. M (motivation) is basically altered by either intrinsic rewards like career advancement or extrinsic reward e.g. financial pay or bonuses. Having regular performance reviews with a good channel of feedback is also another way that could impact the employee's motivation. The workers want to feel that their positions in the company is safe and the work-life is balanced as well as be provided with good career development opportunities. All these can determine the degree of motivation in an organization depending on how well these issues are catered for. Finally O (opportunity) is prompted by creating teamwork contingencies as well as involvement initiatives, communication channels, job rotations as well as job design. This particular feature has been acclaimed by many researchers as the source that marks high-performance working practices out from alternative HR disciplines (Hutchinson 2013).

Improving on performance seems to be at the back of the mind of most business executives. This is why companies all over the globe are constantly trying to motivate their workers in order to ensure that they are productive and at the same time their needs are well-catered for. A well-motivated workforce is easily recognizable as it has common indicators that show the employees enjoy what they do on a daily basis in a company. Some of these signs can be pinpointed and one is able to notice them immediately you walk into an organization: employees always seem to enjoy their work and team work seems to be the order of the day. The focus is always on achieving good results and the energy and robust they exert in the tasks given is quite high, they are willing to give more than a hundred percent towards their work. They are also prepared to go the extra mile be it for the customers, managers or even the company when necessary etc. (Stredwick 2002).

One may say that all these traits cannot occur at one time, but it is not rare either. For those companies which have been able to tap into their employees and put the required measures to ensure that their employees are constantly motivated, they are likely to have these traits and their performance levels are progressive.

Performance Measurement

The ability to measure performance in any organization objectively, depends highly on setting realistic targets that will be able to determine and review prior performance. Having appropriate measures of performance is crucial especially during giving back of feedback, developing more areas for positive performance to thrive as well as allowing room for poor performance to be properly addressed additionally to taking disciplinary action to improve on such areas. It is therefore noteworthy that these measures be viable and reliable in matters concerning promoting the desired performance along with identifying accurately the assessment of achievement (Wilton 2013).

As I discussed earlier there are two major ways to measure performance, the first is to target the results or outcomes of performance where it can be quantified and the second looks at ranking of performance where it cannot be measured quantitatively. Measuring behaviour is quickly gaining more importance as many companies are more concerned on ensuring that their employees display the kind of behaviour and competencies they want likewise to establish the mechanism by which the aspired objectives are accomplished. When measuring performance it is vital to note that the nature of the job or company may determine what kind of measures will be used to assess the performance levels e.g. public parastatals may be more concerned about service delivery to their local citizens and the value placed on the money being utilized to give these services, while Private sector companies may fixated on fiscal revenue in addition to using metrics that help them to make well informed decisions on matters pertaining performance remuneration. Decision makers are therefore advised to make contingent plans when designing performance systems to ensure that they suit the organization's local events as well as flexible and adaptable in the event of unforeseen circumstances on the performance achieved (Wilton 2013).

The setting of objectives requires managers to be acquainted with the abilities and expertise of the employees conjointly with the objectives of the various departments in a company.

Moreover the top management should be in a position to interpret the objectives in relation to tasks and behaviours and then designate the tasks to the most applicable team or individual. To gain the best results, the foundation of this process should be conducted in a manner that is fair and the aim should be to offer jobs that are motivating and provide room for the employees to employ the finesse and expertise they have while at the same time having opportunities for personal development (Pilbeam, Corbridge 2002).

Performance objectives are made in-order for them to be effective in the long run and it has been suggested that this can be attained by having SMART objectives: which means S (specific), M (measurable), A (attainable), R (realistic), and T (time-bounded). Furthermore the employer and employee should agree on the set objectives and should not be imposed. There is usually a high chance of success on those objectives that have been agreed by both parties as they carry more legitimacy than those which are enforced. In the interest of maintaining relevance of these objectives they should be flexible enough to allow room for renegotiation in the event of change of circumstances. Finally they should be auditable so as to allow the ratification of decisions concerning reward and rating. In conclusion the fundamental to the success of performance management is to set objectives and measures that clearly indicate the overall picture of the whole job performance. If the inaccurate dimension of the job is measured then management is bound not to learn anything essential concerning the performance of the employee as well as what their contributions are to the company. Chances are that the workers will react in a negative way to objectives that do not naturally advance the overall performance thus the impact on the individual job satisfaction and motivation will be adversely affected (Wilton 2013).

The Link between Rewards and Motivation

Rewards are termed as a universal and global language as people all over the world tend to respond positively to a work environment that is supportive and caring. Performance and rewards can be a driving force for individuals to accomplish more than their expectations. Comprehending what motivates individuals is quite important for the management to know as it will help them to tap into the various ways to ensure that they are able to successfully motivate their workers (Nieto 2014). So what are rewards? As I mentioned earlier in the introduction, motivation is the inner drive that enables us as individuals to want to take action, rewards on the other hand is what you get after the behaviour or course of action.

Bratton defines rewards as to everything that is financial, non-financial and also psychological awards that are provided by a company to the employees after performing

diligently in their designated duties (Bratton, Gold 2007). It is vital to understand the distinction between these broad categories as they are quite different.

The financial rewards are the earnings or pay a person gets at the end of the month and mainly consists of basic pay e.g. salary or wages and also may include bonuses or conditional pay which could be tied to individual performance as well as overtime pay and commissions. Non-financial rewards on the other hand are intrinsic rewards that come directly from the work individuals undertake additionally to the work environment they are in and bonds formed from the work setting. Feelings of wanting to be valued, praised and yearning for recognition after accomplishing a task are some of the non-financial rewards. Moreover issues of promotion, career advancement and also personal growth and development are considered to be falling under this category. Last but not least are the benefits which are payments that are added to the financial rewards and hold some financial value, they may include paid holiday leave, pension plans, occupational sick leave pay, company car, gym membership, sports club membership, extra annual leave and provision of child care services etc. From the above list it is obvious that some of these benefits are implemented to enhance the commitment of employees as well as cater for their welfare needs (Wilton 2013).

When examining rewards the aspect of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation is imminent, hence it is significant to understand what these two terms mean. Extrinsic motivation focuses more on financial rewards that may include bonuses and pay, commissions, benefits like use of company cars or even cafeterias (Wilton 2013). The rewards from extrinsic motivation are tangible and don't come from the work itself, usually they are created by the supervisors to ensure that employees do what they are supposed to do and follow the rules. For a long time the extrinsic rewards have been deemed as an easy option when it comes to motivating employees as they offer the top management the chance to hover around their subordinates closely supervising to make sure that the rules and regulations are being followed and that work is being done as expected, if not they can decide to withhold rewards. However in today's world the dynamics are changing and individuals are looking for more than a fat check in their account. Having a chance to work in an environment that is innovative, challenging and interesting is something that more people are keen to engage in as it offers more opportunities for personal development: this is where intrinsic motivation comes in (Thomas 2002).

Intrinsic motivation lies more on the lines of aiming to satisfy employee's psychological needs which may include recognition of accomplishment, provision of challenging work that is interesting as well as favourable chances for both personal and professional development. Management of rewards certainly traverses multiple facets of human resource management including training and development, employee relations as well as management of performance. Organizations therefore are encouraged to create reward systems that are beneficial to the employees and their employers in order to maintain a bilateral employment relationship between them (Wilton 2013). Further-more as far as motivation is concerned the expectancy theories of motivation has clearly indicated that

employees can only feel motivated if the rewards they are receiving are valued by the recipients, if the one receiving the reward does not really value it then it is highly likely that he or she will not be motivated by it (Wilton 2013). Rewards can be regarded as elements that could shape the attitudes of employees towards their job and company. If they are dissatisfied with the way the reward packages have been made then it is likely for them to react with their actions. Their performance will probably go down and also the intent to quit the job or change jobs is highly likely. In worst case scenario dysfunctional behaviour such as strikes are likely to occur (Wilton 2013).

The motivation theories in chapter 2 offer some suggestions on how rewards can be implemented to elicit motivation like behaviour. The expectancy theory of motivation suggests that individuals have different preferences towards particular outcomes. Identifying what outcomes or rewards are important to the individuals and the value they have placed on certain outcomes is vital. E.g. Organizations that have generalized reward packages of pay and allowances may face the problem of motivating everyone in the company. This is because as previously mentioned in the introduction money may not be a motivator for everyone. Some people value having recognition for a job well done over banking a fat check. Reward packages should therefore be individualized to ensure they cater for the intended purpose. Organizations should try and find out what type of rewards motivate their staff and actualize such rewards (Hutchinson 2013). Employees whom are satisfied with their reward packages show some commitment level to the job and motivation will be evident. Therefore top management should keep this in mind when forming the reward packages to ensure that the rewards they give out are satisfying the employees' needs.

